

**An alternative interpretation of the 40..42 GHz experiments on yeast cells around 1980
- a really far fetched contemplation - or maybe a hint to look for axions there**

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- *There was a considerable excitement in the early 80th from the results of mm wave yeast cell experiments by Grundler, Keilmann et al at the Max Planck Institute in Stuttgart / Germany claiming that they have found the first clear experimental evidence for non (or sub-) thermal biological effects from EM radiation via significant changes comparing the growth rate of (faint mm wave) irradiated and non irradiated yeast cells.*
- *The experiments were carried out with great care and diligence (MANY papers)*
- *However those results could never be replicated despite several attempts elsewhere.*
- *At this time old style microwave generation equipment like (phaselocked) klystrons and travelling wave amplifiers as well as lots of circulators and isolators were used. (strong static magnetic fields + microwaves)*
(Grundler, Keilmann, Fröhlich, Physics letters 62A no 6 Sept 1977 » resonant growth rate response of yeast cells irradiated by weak microwaves »)
- *Perhaps accidentally there were some axions or similar DE/DM generated in this setup which were « felt » by the yeast solutions and had an impact on the growth rate...those cells have lots of dielectric boundaries..and often very strong internal E- fields at the cell membranes..*
Could this be a hint to have a closer look into the region 40..42 GHz with todays experimental setups for axion and DM search?
- *Or just place a Petri dish with some yeast culturus in Agar onto one of the dielectric disks « booster » in MADMAX (at room temperature) and listen with the very sensitive radiometer receiver for narrowband weak mm wave signals (around 42 GHz) from the yeast culture (which were claimed to exist (Fröhlich theory), but never really measured.)*